

COUPLING OF PLANAR GROWTH AND MATRIX CRACKING IN MODE III DELAMINATION TOUGHNESS TESTING

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1 Introduction

Recently, a new split-shear torsion (SST) test was introduced to determine the mode III delamination toughness (G_{IIIc}) of unidirectional laminated composites [1, 2]. The SST is conceptually similar to mode III loading of the shear-torsion-bending (STB) test [3]. SST tests performed on specimens with and without preimplanted edge delaminations have been shown to produce the same toughness as mode III STB tests using specimens of identical material and geometry [1, 2]. To further assess whether the SST was yielding a true value of G_{IIIc} , tests were also performed over a range of delamination lengths. However, toughness was observed to decrease with increasing delamination length [1, 2]. This is not an observation unique to SST; indeed, variations of G_{IIIc} with delamination length have also been observed in mode III with both the modified split cantilever beam (MSCB) [4, 5] and the edge crack torsion (ECT) [6-9] tests. The MSCB is a split beam test similar to the SST and shows an analogous decreasing trend in apparent G_{IIIc} with increasing delamination length, whereas the apparent value of G_{IIIc} typically increases with delamination length in the ECT. Here, the term “apparent G_{IIIc} ” is used, as the geometrical dependence indicates that the tests are not yielding a true material property. Considering the number of research groups and the variety of test methods and materials studied, it now appears increasingly unlikely that the observed geometric dependencies are all artifacts of the various test methods. Rather, it is more probable that there is an effect related to mode III growth that is not yet fully understood.

To address the above, parallel and coordinated studies were initiated using the SST test, as described in the preliminary work in Ref. [2] and in the study that follows, and using the ECT test, as described in Ref. [10]. Initially, specimens tested in both configurations were sectioned transversely, i.e., parallel to the delamination front and perpendicular

to the plane of the delamination, at locations immediately ahead of the delamination front. This approach has apparently not been taken in the past; previously, composite mode III specimens have only been sectioned in a plane that is parallel to that of the delamination [3, 6-8]. This new approach showed that, in both specimen types, matrix cracks were readily observable in a plane transverse to the delamination. These cracks were oriented at approximately 45° and extended into the plies above and below the delamination [2, 10]. These initial section cuts were performed on specimens in which delamination growth had already occurred, and therefore did not provide any information on whether the matrix cracks initiated before, concurrently with, or subsequent to the initiation of planar delamination advance. If these cracks initiate prior to or concurrently with planar growth, then this would indicate that delamination advance is very different from what is generally assumed. It follows that neither test (SST or ECT) would measure mode III toughness in the conventional sense, and that the presence of these cracks may be responsible for the observed dependence of toughness on test geometry.

The overarching goal of this work and its companion study [10] is to assess the influence of the matrix cracks described above on the perceived toughness in common mode III delamination toughness tests. To that end, the first goal of this investigation is to assess whether the matrix cracks that have been observed at the delamination front in delaminated SST specimens are already present when delamination advance initiates. The second, related goal, is to assess the specific progression of “damage,” used here to denote the accumulation and growth of matrix cracks, that is associated with what has heretofore been considered mode III growth. The third and final goal is to relate these findings to observations of the apparent mode III toughness from SST tests and, to whatever extent possible, other mode III delamination toughness tests.

2 Experimental Methodology

2.1 Test and Specimen Geometries

Figure 1 presents a schematic representation of the SST test. The fixture may be used in a uniaxial load frame in the configuration shown. One load block is attached to the load cell, and the other to the actuator. The location of the bottom load block is adjustable in the z-direction via slots in order to accommodate specimens of various thicknesses. Both load blocks contain two holes sized for bolts. Load tabs are used to transfer load from the fixture to the specimen through these bolts. The load tabs are 50.8 mm x 31.75 mm x 6.25 mm thick, and contain two threaded bolt holes which are positioned to be as close to the specimen as possible without contacting it. Load tabs, which are more clearly visible in Fig. 2, are bonded to the specimen using Hysol EA 9309.3 NA adhesive, which is a two-part epoxy containing 0.13 mm diameter glass beads to enforce a consistent and uniform thickness bond line. These load blocks and load tabs are slightly different from those used previously. These changes and their motivation are described subsequently.

Nomenclature for an SST test specimen is also presented in Fig. 1. The enforced boundary conditions of the SST test at the cracked end are identical to those for the STB test, where the cracked legs are constrained to move in translation in the y-direction only [3]. To accomplish this condition, the load blocks and load tabs force the slopes of the cracked ends of the specimen to be zero, and prevents them from translating in the x- or z-directions. The specimens used in this study have width $B=25.4$ mm, thickness from $2h=3.0-3.3$ mm, and delamination lengths from $a=31.75-76.2$ mm. In previous works [1, 2], this geometry was called the non-edge delaminated SST in order to differentiate it from a geometry known as edge delaminated SST. Edge delaminations, which were introduced in the original STB test [3], may be preimplanted at the midplane during manufacture and will cause the mode III energy release rate (ERR) to be essentially uniform across the delamination front [1-3]. However, Ref. [2] showed that testing specimens with or without edge delaminations resulted in essentially the same value of toughness. Because specimens without edge delaminations are easier to manufacture, no specimens in this work contain edge delaminations. That is, all tests were performed using the non-edge delaminated geometry.

2.2 Specimen Preparation and Modulus Testing

This study used primarily unidirectional 26 ply IM7/977-3 test specimens, which produced specimens that had a thickness of $2h=3.3$ mm. These were chosen based on the results in Refs. [1-3]. All IM7/977-3 test specimens were fabricated at the Syracuse University Composite Materials Laboratory using an autoclave and the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle. Additionally, a small number of tests were conducted using unidirectional 24 ply IM7/8552 test specimens, which produced specimens that had a thickness of $2h=3.0$ mm. All IM7/8552 specimens were fabricated at NASA Langley Research Center in a hot press.

As described above, specimens were fabricated with a variety of preimplanted insert lengths. These were generally fabricated following the procedure described in Refs. [1, 2]. For IM7/977-3, two 12.7 μm thick Teflon sheets were cut into rectangles and placed at the midplane of a 305 mm x 305 mm plate during manufacture. The sheets were oriented orthogonally to the fiber direction and located at the ends to create the desired insert length. Plates were debulked after the 8th and 16th plies. This was done to address an issue of somewhat large porosity that was observed in previous specimens [2]. Subsequent to manufacture, the plates were cut parallel to the fiber direction (perpendicular to the Teflon inserts) into ten 25.4 mm wide strips. Each of these strips contained a Teflon insert at each end, thereby producing 20 specimens. The IM7/8552 specimens were fabricated using a Teflon sheet at one end only, which resulted in 10 specimens. In total, three plates were fabricated: two of IM7/977-3 and one of IM7/8552.

After cutting, an alignment jig was used to bond the specimens to rectangular, machined low-carbon steel load tabs. To this end, the threaded bolt holes in the tabs were secured to two sides of the jig, and a specimen was sandwiched between them. Alignment rails were used to orient the specimen correctly with respect to the load tabs. After tabbing, specimens were c-scanned to obtain a pre-test scan of the delamination front. After testing, specimens were post-test c-scanned to identify whether the delamination front had advanced. Both scans included the tabbed region that acted as a common datum to compare images.

As will be discussed in what follows, the data reduction method used for the SST test is sensitive to the values of the axial and shear moduli. Thus, in addition to obtaining test specimens, two specimens

were cut from the non-delaminated portion of each composite plate manufactured and were used to determine the axial modulus (E_{11}) following Ref. [11]. Relatively little variation has been observed in these values for all plates made [1-3], with coefficients of variation (CVs) on the order of 2%. Testing to determine the shear modulus (G_{12}) followed Ref. [12] and also produced relatively tight distributions, with CVs on the order of 6%. For IM7/977-3, $E_{11}=163.8$ GPa and $G_{12}=4.95$ GPa. For IM7/8552, $E_{11}=187.2$ GPa and $G_{12}=7.33$ GPa.

2.3 ERR Determination

A compliance calibration technique was considered for data reduction when the SST test was first introduced [1]. However, this approach could not be implemented due to the small deflections in the test, the need to use load tabs to avoid significant local deformations in the composite specimen, and a small amount of nonlinearity that occurs in the load versus displacement response [1]. Although this latter issue was mitigated by the redesigned load blocks and load tabs, it is unclear whether a multi-specimen compliance calibration technique (as used for the ECT [6-9]) would be accurate. As such, in this work the original, finite element-based approach to data reduction for the SST test [1, 2] is utilized.

Finite element (FE) analyses conducted for this work utilized essentially the same model and mesh as those used in Refs. [1, 2]; only the load tabs were modified to reflect the new design presented herein. The mesh uses 20 noded quadrat brick elements, and builds on the original FE work performed for the STB [3]. ERRs are computed along the delamination front using the virtual crack closure technique. As described in [1, 2], a series of mesh refinement studies showed that the FE predictions were insensitive to the mesh used, and that this mesh was sufficiently refined to capture the variation in ERR across the specimen's width.

Figure 3 presents a plot of local normalized mode II and III ERR components across the width of an SST specimen. The mode components are normalized to the total average ERR (G_{avg}), defined as the average value for the full width of the specimen [1-3]. The mode I component is negligible and is therefore not presented. The trends evidenced in Fig. 3 are typical for specimens of all delamination lengths used in this work, and the results do not depend on material properties. Tests at all delamination lengths are predominantly mode III. The value of $G_{III-avg}/G_{avg}$ for specimens with delamination lengths of $a=76.2$ mm is 0.98, where $G_{III-avg}$ is the average mode III ERR for the full width of the specimen, and $G_{III-avg}/G_{avg}$

increases with decreasing delamination length. Fig. 3 shows that G_{III} is a maximum at the center of the width and decreases near the free edges. The mode II ERR is essentially zero in the central portion of the specimen and remains insignificant across the majority of the specimen's width. Large values of mode II (single symbol) at each edge are confined to the outermost 0.5-1% of the specimen's width and do not influence growth [1, 2].

Similar to that reported for MSCB tests [4, 5], the distribution of ERR across the specimen's width shown in Fig. 3 indicates that delamination advance will initiate in the center of the specimen, and this has been verified experimentally [1, 2]. This substantiates the assertion that delamination advance occurs under pure mode III conditions. Moreover, in contrast to the MSCB, there is a "plateau" in the load versus displacement response that corresponds to delamination initiation in the SST. This makes the load corresponding to delamination onset relatively easy to determine. Thus, considering Fig. 3, delamination toughness is calculated using the peak value of the local ERR (G_{III-pk}), i.e., at the center of the specimen, computed at the delamination onset load. Fundamentally, this is determined using the FE results. However, rather than perform a FE analysis of each individual specimen, an approach is adopted that is analogous to that used in Refs. [1-3]. Here, the equation developed for the mode III ERR in an STB specimen is modified to yield:

$$G_{III-pk} = C_f(a) \frac{P^2}{B^2 h G_{12}} \left(0.66 + 1.15 \sqrt{\frac{G_{12}}{E_{11}}} \right) \quad (1)$$

In the above, $C_f(a)$ is a correction factor that depends on delamination length. It is extracted from a FE analysis of a single specimen at each delamination length such that G_{III-pk} given by Eq. (1) agrees with the corresponding FE prediction. The primary benefit for a single material is that this allows the specific values of width, B , and thickness, $2h$, to be utilized for each specimen tested. Further, it allows specimens of other materials and/or thicknesses to be tested, providing that the same delamination lengths are used. The validity of Eq. (1) has been verified over a range of material and geometric properties for both SST and STB geometries [1-3] and was also validated as part of this study.

Following the above procedure for the specimens considered herein yielded $C_f=1.93$ for $a=31.75$ mm, $C_f=2.84$ for $a=54.0$ mm, and $C_f=3.76$ for $a=76.2$ mm. These values are used subsequently along with Eq. (1) to determine G_{III-pk} as a function of the

applied load, P , and to determine the apparent value of G_{IIIc} . This is taken as the value of G_{III-pk} when $P=P_c$, where P_c is defined to be the “critical value,” i.e., the delamination onset load. We point out that the correction factors presented above are approximately 2% different from those given in Refs. [1, 2] due to the modified load block and load tab designs.

2.4 Evaluation Procedures

SST tests were performed at three delamination lengths: $a=31.75$, 54.0 and 76.2 mm. Some of these specimens were tested to the critical fracture load, P_c . These are referred to as “toughness test specimens” because they were used to determine the apparent toughness at the various delamination lengths. Other tests were stopped at a lower load, i.e., before delamination occurred. These are referred to as “damage progression specimens” because they were used to investigate the progression of damage leading up to delamination. As described previously, a c-scan was performed subsequent to all tests. In specimens tested to fracture, the c-scan served to verify that delamination advance occurred over the majority of the specimen’s width. In damage progression specimens, the c-scan was used to confirm that no delamination advance had occurred. That is, if a specimen was tested to a load near P_c , the c-scan was used to verify that the delamination front did not advance.

Both toughness test specimens and damage progression specimens were sectioned for microscopic examination after testing. Toughness test specimens were sectioned in order to compare to previous results [2], where matrix cracks were visible in the region of delamination advance in IM7/977-3 specimens cut from a different plate. These previous specimens had somewhat large porosity, and were tested using an earlier load tab design. As these earlier observations motivated the present study, it was important to determine whether cross-sections within the specimens tested herein – which were manufactured using the debulking procedure and which used the new load tab design – appeared essentially the same. Thus, a transverse cut exposing the y - z plane (cf. Fig. 1) was made in these specimens just ahead of the original Teflon insert in the newly delaminated region. This corresponded to the location of the section cuts made in Ref. [2]. Damage progression specimens were also cut transversely, exposing the y - z plane. This was done in order to assess whether matrix cracking occurred prior to delamination advance and, if so, its extent. To this end, damage progression specimens were

sectioned in the region of the Teflon insert, fairly close to the delamination front. Each cross section was then carefully ground until the visible plane was the same as the edge of the Teflon insert, and the delamination front was visible. For both specimen types, the cut sections were potted in epoxy, polished, and cleaned according to Ref. [13]. These cross sections were then examined using optical microscopy, and photomicrographs were taken. If it was desired to obtain images further ahead of the initial cross section, the potted specimen was ground, then polished and cleaned repeatedly, allowing multiple planes to be imaged.

3 Results

3.1 Apparent G_{IIIc} Testing

Figure 4 presents a typical load versus deflection plot for an SST test of a specimen with delamination length $a=76.2$ mm. For all delamination lengths and either material, the trends are essentially the same. For all tests, the load versus deflection response is not quite linear. The amount of nonlinearity increases with increasing load up to a “load plateau.” This load plateau corresponds to the initiation of mode III growth, and is thus the critical load, P_c , for fracture. This was verified experimentally [1, 2] in a process whereby specimens were successively loaded, unloaded, and c-scanned to view the delamination front. No delamination growth occurred until the load plateau. In an extension of the same study it was found that in SST tests, at the load plateau, delamination growth always initiates in the center of the specimen, as predicted by the FE analysis [1, 2].

Figure 5 presents a plot of apparent G_{IIIc} versus delamination length for $a=31.75$ mm, $a=54.0$ mm, and $a=76.2$ mm. These data were obtained from tests of 14 specimens that were cut from two different plates (I13 and I14) of IM7/977-3. A trend of decreasing apparent toughness with increasing delamination length is clearly seen, and is similar to that observed in previous studies using the SST test [1, 2]. The average values for apparent G_{IIIc} along with the associated CVs are presented in Table 1.

The toughnesses presented in Fig. 5 are somewhat lower than those presented in Ref. [2] for the same material and delamination lengths. The likely cause of this relates to the change in load tab and load block design. In the previous design, bolts between the load blocks and load tabs were not used. Rather, load transfer was achieved via load pins that were press-fit into the load blocks and where mated to semi-circular machined cut-outs in the load tabs.

However, it was found that, due to small specimen-to-specimen variations in load tab machining, each specimen underwent small rotations while the load pins “seated,” i.e., while they achieved full contact within each semi-circular cut-out with increasing load. This was accompanied by a region of nonlinear load versus deflection response at low loads, and is what motivated the load tab and load block redesign. Thus, it is possible that the current approach is closer to a true zero slope boundary condition within the tabbed region and the resulting change in ERR – which would be more pronounced at shorter delamination lengths – is what accounts for the observed differences in the current versus previous values of apparent G_{IIIc} . Alternatively, given the observed dependence of the apparent toughness on geometry illustrated in Fig. 5, it is also possible that there are other influencing factors. This difficulty of separating out material versus structural effects is one of the key problems with current mode III testing, and is one that the present study hopes to address.

A limited number of toughness tests were conducted for IM7/8552. Two tests were performed at a delamination length of $a=31.75$ mm and yielded an average toughness of $G_{IIIc}=556$ J/m². One test was performed at a delamination length of $a=76.2$ mm yielding $G_{IIIc}=262$ J/m². Only a small number of specimens were tested because the main focus of using this material was to compare the damage progression test data with that of IM7/977-3. However, in order to interpret damage progression specimen test data, it is useful to know the approximate apparent $G_{IIIc}(a)$ relation. Even with the limited set of data for this material, a distinct variation of apparent G_{IIIc} with delamination length can be seen.

3.2 Damage Progression Testing

Damage progression testing was performed on IM7/977-3 specimens at two delamination lengths. Four specimens were tested at a delamination length of $a=31.75$ mm and three specimens were tested at a delamination length of $a=76.2$ mm. These tests were stopped prior to the onset of delamination growth, i.e., prior to the load plateau, but otherwise were conducted identically to the delamination toughness tests. After testing, all specimens were c-scanned to verify that no growth occurred.

As described previously, the goals of the damage initiation tests were to identify the onset and progression of matrix cracking and how this relates to delamination advance. To this end, damage progression tests were stopped at loads where the

apparent G_{III} was less than the apparent G_{IIIc} obtained for specimens with the same delamination length, as seen in Table 2. For all delamination lengths, 70% of G_{IIIc} approximately corresponds to the onset of increasing nonlinearity (cf. Fig. 4), and was chosen as the lower limit for stopping a test. It is important to note that, because of the delamination length dependency in apparent G_{IIIc} , tests on specimens with two different delamination lengths that were stopped at the same percentage of their respective G_{IIIc} were stopped at different values of apparent G_{III} .

3.3 Photomicroscopy

A photomicrograph of a specimen with delamination length $a=31.75$ mm where the delamination front has advanced is shown in Fig. 6. This photomicrograph was taken from one of the toughness test specimens, and the delamination fronts of toughness test specimens with other length delaminations look similar. The section shown in Fig. 6 is in a region where delamination growth occurred. The thick, jagged path running horizontally is the interlaminar delamination. This photomicrograph displays 12 plies of material, and the plies of the composite are evident above and below the plane of delamination. Also evident are three matrix cracks emanating from the midplane. These matrix cracks extend both above and below the midplane and are growing along a plane oriented at approximately 45° to the x - y plane (cf. Fig. 1). From the arrows superimposed on Fig. 6 indicating the loading direction – and therefore the direction of shear stress, τ_{yz} – it is observed that this orientation is perpendicular to the direction of the maximum principal tensile stress near the delamination tip. Initiation of small cracks in this orientation prior to mode III advance of a macro-crack has been observed in mode III fracture of homogeneous materials and has been attributed to the tensile stresses associated with the K_{III} field [14, 15], where K_{III} is the mode III stress intensity factor. These observations also agree with what was observed in Refs. [2, 10], as well as for the IM7/8552 specimens tested in this study (described subsequently).

The image shown in Fig. 6 represents only a small percentage of the specimen’s width. The complete photomicroscopic evaluation indicates that matrix cracks are present across the entire width of each specimen, and vary in size and spacing. In the specimens studied herein of width $B=25.4$ mm and thickness $2h=3.3$ mm, there may be anywhere from 30 – 80 matrix cracks visible with lengths ranging from 0.5 mm to 2.3 mm. Smaller cracks are likely

present, but are not easily measureable. The delamination front in Fig. 6 and those observed in other images taken from the toughness test specimens do not differ in any significant way from those presented in Ref. [2]. This corroborates the conclusion in this earlier work that the presence of small intralaminar voids in the material, i.e., within plies, does not influence the onset or location of the matrix cracks. They also indicate that there are no apparent changes in the post-growth damage state as a result of the redesigned load tabs.

A series of photomicrographs obtained from damage progression specimens with delamination lengths $a=76.2$ mm are presented in Fig. 7. Note that these images are at approximately ten times higher magnification than the image in Fig. 6. The three images in Fig. 7 are from three different damage progression test specimens. All sections are taken just ahead of the Teflon insert, and no delamination advance occurred in any of these specimens. The images are ordered based on increasing maximum G_{III} . This is expressed in the figure caption as percentage of apparent G_{IIIc} , and the corresponding values of G_{III} are presented in Table 2.

The specimen shown in Fig. 7a, for which the maximum ERR was 73% of G_{IIIc} , primarily has matrix cracks in the resin rich interlayer ahead of the Teflon insert. In this figure, matrix cracks have just begun to initiate. Matrix cracks are present across the middle 25-75% of the specimen's width, and are concentrated in the center where the local ERR is highest. A few of the cracks extend one or two fiber diameters into one of the adjacent plies, but the majority are in the resin interlayer only. In general, the matrix cracks in this specimen, and in other specimens loaded to similar levels, appear to initiate either at the interface between a fiber and the matrix material, or at small (fiber-diameter or less) voids within or immediately adjacent to the resin-rich region between plies. For example, the matrix crack indicated by the arrow in Fig. 7a appears to have initiated at a small void between two fibers. The stress concentrations associated with these small local defects provide preferential initiation points for the cracks. However, the spacing of the cracks is not dictated by the void locations, and the matrix cracks initiate whether or not they are present. Thus, it is likely that their presence is not affecting the results. Additionally, while the local crack initiation may be at an angle other than 45° from the x-y plane based on the location or orientation of the defect, it may be observed in Fig. 7a that the crack rapidly orients

itself perpendicular to the direction of maximum tensile stress.

The specimen shown in Fig. 7b was tested to 88% of G_{IIIc} . This figure shows the damage evolution that occurs with increasing load. In comparison to the specimen of Fig. 7a, this specimen had a higher number of matrix cracks, and the distribution of cracks extended closer to the edges (middle 10-90% of width) than the specimen from Fig. 7a. Additionally, the matrix cracks are seen to extend further into the plies, although they do not generally travel more than 10 fiber diameters.

Figure 7c shows a specimen that was loaded to 91% of apparent G_{IIIc} . Matrix cracks were visible across the full width of this specimen and, as may be observed in the figure, extend through entire plies. The largest cracks were observed in the center region of the specimen where the ERR is highest (cf. Fig. 3). Further, as can be seen on the right side of Fig. 7c, some of the matrix cracks also have horizontal branches that extend along the midplane. In some instances these horizontal cracks intersect and connect two transverse (45°) cracks. However, this is not always the case, and there are many transverse cracks that have grown into the adjacent plies which do not have horizontal cracks associated with them. Those horizontal cracks that do occur, which were not observed in the specimens tested to lower loads, are the precursors to delamination advance.

The sequence of images of Fig. 7 clearly shows how delamination advance evolves. With additional load, the entire "system of damage" of Fig. 7c connects and advances to produce a state similar to that shown in Fig. 6. Note, however, that the image in Fig. 7c is prior to the conventional definition of delamination advance, i.e., as would be indicated by a plateau in the load-deflection response or as evident by c-scan. Combining this image with similar images from other damage progression specimens tested near their apparent G_{IIIc} indicates that a significant amount of matrix cracking always occurs prior to macroscopic delamination advance, and that matrix cracking and delamination advance are intrinsically coupled in this material.

Damage progression tests for IM7/8552 specimens were also conducted. Two specimens at delamination lengths of $a=31.75$ mm and three specimens at delamination lengths of $a=76.2$ mm were tested. Photomicrographs of the resin interlayer region ahead of the Teflon insert for the specimens with delamination lengths of $a=76.2$ mm are shown in Fig. 8. Figure 8a is at essentially the same

percentage of apparent G_{IIIc} as the specimen shown in Fig. 7a. Figure 8b is at 100% of apparent G_{IIIc} , i.e., this test was stopped at a value of apparent G_{III} equal to 262 J/m^2 , the same apparent ERR at which growth occurred in the delamination toughness test specimen. However, there was no evidence of delamination growth in this specimen: no load-plateau appeared, and a post-test c-scan did not show any differences from the pre-test scan. Thus, this image is similar to that of Fig. 7c, in that it represents the state of damage shortly before macroscopic delamination advance will be observed. A unique feature of the section shown in Fig. 8b is that this image was taken further ahead of the Teflon insert than the other images included herein. This section was cut approximately 0.25 mm ahead of the insert, i.e., in the uncracked region. This image clearly shows that the matrix cracks grow into the uncracked region prior to delamination advance.

Comparisons of Fig. 8a and Fig. 7a and of Fig. 8b and Fig. 7c show that the progression of damage is essentially the same for IM7/8552 as for IM7/977-3. As indicated by the arrows, Fig. 8a shows the initiation of the matrix cracks preferentially occurring at discontinuities between the resin and fibers. Crack sizes and spacing in this specimen were not significantly different from those observed in the specimen of Fig. 7a. The specimen shown in Fig. 8b has matrix cracks that are inclined at 45° that go through the interlaminar region and, as indicated by the arrows, have grown into the adjacent ply. Similar to Fig. 7c, some of the cracks from the specimen in Fig. 8b showed horizontal branches at the specimen's midplane, and in some instances these horizontal branches connected pairs of inclined cracks.

The above observations indicate that matrix cracking will always precede planar delamination growth in unidirectional SST specimens in the materials tested and, as described below, it is likely that this will be true for other laminated unidirectional polymeric matrix composites. The matrix cracks form immediately ahead of the delamination front within the resin rich interlayer at a load well below that required for macroscopic delamination advance. As the load continues to increase, these cracks grow transversely, at an inclination of approximately 45° , into their neighboring plies. Figure 8b shows that these cracks extend a small distance into the uncracked region and, although not investigated in this work, it is possible that they display the characteristic "parahelical shape" [14, 15] observed in homogeneous materials. With increasing load the

matrix cracks continue to grow through additional adjacent plies. Horizontal branches also initiate and grow along the laminate's midplane and begin to connect the transverse cracks. Initially, these do not extend into the uncracked region a sufficient amount to be detectable by c-scan, nor do they span the entire specimen width as viewed from the transverse cuts taken herein. However, this changes with increasing load, and these precursors to delamination advance ultimately connect and advance, concurrently with the transverse matrix cracks, into the uncracked region in what is typically taken to be macroscopic delamination growth. This process corresponds to the sequence of events given in Figs. 7a, 7b, 7c, and finally Fig. 6.

An important observation related to the mechanistic understanding of the above behavior is that, in both materials used in this study, there is a visible similarity between the damage state in specimens with different delamination lengths that are at comparable percentages of their apparent $G_{IIIc(a)}$. For example, specimens I14-10B and I13-9T (cf. Table 2) are at similar values of apparent G_{III}/G_{IIIc} and are similar in terms of both length and number of matrix cracks. Note, however, that these two specimens were tested to very different values of apparent G_{III} . The same is true for a comparison of specimens I14-12B and I14-3T. This similarity could also be expressed in terms of the percentage of average delamination onset load at any delamination length. What is interesting is that this correspondence cannot be expressed using conventional linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) parameters, such as G_{III} or K_{III} , as one might expect if matrix cracking is used to explain the apparent dependence of toughness on delamination length. However, it is important to note that the predictions of ERR are based on an analysis that assumes an uncracked matrix, and these predictions are therefore only valid until matrix cracking initiates. At that point, local stress intensity factors associated with the newly formed cracks will change the near-tip field from that predicted by the original analysis.

It is possible that the true initiation of cracking occurs at the same value of G_{III} for specimens with different delamination lengths. This is what would be predicted by LEFM and the assumption that the cracks initiate from the maximum tensile stress induced by the K_{III} field. This could not have been deduced from the current study, however, as the lowest load for any damage progression test was 73% of the apparent $G_{IIIc(a)}$. This was done in an

effort to first establish whether or not matrix cracks occurred prior to delamination onset. With this established, it appears that additional study would be required to deduce the exact onset point of matrix cracking. However, in order to mechanistically explain the observed dependence of toughness on delamination length, one would also need to perform analyses that account for the true state of damage evolution up to some critical state where macroscopic delamination advance occurs.

4 Implications for Mode III Testing

Similar to what is observed in homogeneous materials, this study has shown that initiation and growth of cracks at an inclination of 45° to the direction of mode III growth will correspond to the first “fracture event” in mode III testing of unidirectional laminated carbon/epoxy composites. Additional growth and evolution of these matrix cracks then occurs until they link, and macroscopic cumulative advance appears at what is typically taken as the delamination onset load. From previous discussions, it is clear that this is quite different than the assumptions in any mechanistic model used to extract a mode III toughness – including the assumptions used in a compliance calibration method of data reduction – and therefore invalidates the critical values of ERR obtained from the associated mode III tests. Rather, the apparent G_{IIIc} values that are obtained are a structural property. The variation in G_{IIIc} with delamination length that is obtained is therefore not surprising, as a material property is not being measured. It follows that the lack of a direct correlation of the damage observations herein to the measured variations in $G_{IIIc}(a)$ is also not surprising, as the apparent toughness is based on an analysis that does not accurately reflect the mechanics or physics of the physical problem.

While the present study concentrated on carbon/epoxy composites, it is hard to envision that the sequence of events would be different in any unidirectional laminated polymeric matrix composite. Fundamentally, the observations herein confirm the well-documented preference for mode I growth in homogeneous materials, regardless of the mode mixity of the loading, and the architecture of the reinforcing fibers is such that it does not significantly alter this situation. Thus, it is likely that the mechanisms described herein also explain the dependence of toughness on delamination length that has been observed in unidirectional MSCB tests [4, 5]. For ECT tests, we note that the laminate layup is

typically chosen such that mode III delamination advance will occur along the direction of the fibers of the two bounding plies. That is, it is locally identical to the SST geometry. One would therefore expect that “mode III growth” in conventional ECT tests would proceed similarly to what was observed herein, and this has been confirmed in a parallel study [10]. Thus, the apparent variation in toughness with delamination length in ECT testing is also explained by the same mechanisms at those observed herein.

The above observations have significant implications with respect to the current conceptual framework for the assessment of toughness and the prediction of delamination growth under mode III or mixed-mode conditions where mode III is present. While it is possible that using other ply angles to bound the interface for mode III testing may be used to constrain the matrix cracks to the interlaminar region and therefore obtain a value of G_{IIIc} that is independent of delamination length for some range of bounding ply angles, in practice delamination advance will often occur under conditions with coupled matrix cracking, and it is not clear whether this approach will have any appreciable practical applicability. Further, considering the strong dependence of the apparent toughness on test geometry for those bounding ply angles where coupled matrix cracking occurs, it is also unlikely that approaches which express toughness as a function of bounding ply angle, such as those used in modes I and II [16], will be valid.

5 Conclusions

The progression of damage in a mode III delamination toughness test was examined to determine if transverse matrix cracks initiate prior to planar advance of a preimplanted interlaminar delamination. To this end, specimens from two different carbon/epoxy materials were tested in an SST fixture using an improved test geometry compared to that introduced previously. A series of tests examining damage progression found that the first inelastic event consists of the initiation of matrix cracks within the resin rich region between plies. These cracks were inclined to the direction of loading and were perpendicular to the direction of maximum tensile stress. With increasing load, they were observed to extend into the neighboring plies and develop a horizontally branched network prior to any observations or indications of planar delamination advance. The size, distribution and density of these cracks is well beyond that which

would be required to cause ERR predictions, using any mechanistic model or set of assumptions that considers an uncracked matrix, to no longer be accurate. It is likely that this will always be true for unidirectional SST and MSCB specimens and for ECT specimens using conventional stacking sequences that are fabricated from continuous fiber polymeric matrix composites. It therefore appears that this explains the observed dependence of test geometry on the apparent mode III toughness that has been reported in the literature for these three test methods. Further, the fact that the nature of mode III advance in laminated polymeric composites is quite different from that which has heretofore been assumed has important philosophical and practical ramifications on approaches for assessing toughness and predicting delamination growth in these materials.

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Fig. 1. Schematic of the SST test.

Fig. 2. SST specimen with load tabs.

Table 1. Delamination toughness data for IM7/977-3.

Delam. Length (mm)	Apparent G_{IIIc} (J/m^2)	CV (%)
31.75	760	9.7
54.0	681	1.3
76.2	469	7.1

Table 2. Damage progression test stopping points for IM7/977-3.

Spec.	Delam. Length (mm)	Apparent G_{III} at Test Stop (J/m^2)	Percent of Apparent G_{IIIc}
I14-10B	31.75	581	76
I14-9B	31.75	601	79
I13-11B	31.75	608	80
I14-12B	31.75	638	84
I13-9T	76.2	343	73
I14-3T	76.2	413	88
I13-10T	76.2	427	91

Fig 3. Localized ERR across the specimen width for SST test from FE analysis.

Fig. 4. Typical load versus deflection plot.

Fig. 5. Apparent G_{IIIc} vs. delamination length for IM7/977-3.

Fig. 6. Photomicrograph of delamination front, I13-7B, $a=31.75$ mm, apparent $G_{IIIc}=723$ J/m².

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 7. Photomicrographs of IM7/977-3 delamination fronts, $a=76.2$ mm. (a) I13-9T, 73% of apparent G_{IIIc} . (b) I14-3T, 88% of apparent G_{IIIc} . (c) I13-10T, 91% of apparent G_{IIIc} .

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8. Photomicrographs of IM7/8552 delamination fronts, $a=76.2$ mm. (a) J2-5, 75% of apparent G_{IIIc} . (b) J2-9, 100% of apparent G_{IIIc} .

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